

ZOONOSES ARE COMMON AND TREATABLE CAUSE OF MYALGIC ENCEPHALOMYELITIS/ CHRONIC FATIGUE SYNDROME (ME/CFS). Study of 392 cases confirmed by direct visualization of Babesia, Bartonella, Borrelia and Mycoplasma in blood and clinical improvement with antimicrobial treatment.

Aguirre-Chang, Gustavo¹; Tarello, Walter² and Trujillo, Aurora³. ResearchGate. January 8, 2026.

1: Consultant at the Apheresis Center Clinic, Cyprus. 2: Microscopic Diagnosis: tarello@gmail.com United Arab Emirates 1 y 3: Directors at Sistemas de Gestión en Salud y Trabajo (SIGESA) and Suppliers at Clínica San Pablo. Lima, Perú.

BACKGROUND.

Myalgic Encephalomyelitis/Chronic Fatigue Syndrome (ME/CFS) is a chronic acquired disease that is reported in a significant number of countries in Europe, North America and Australia. As it is an acquired disease, the main etiological probability is that ME/CFS is caused by environmental or external agents, mainly pathogenic microorganisms capable of generating persistent or chronic infections.

The countries mentioned are endemic areas of various zoonoses, that is, infections transmitted from animals to humans. Most of these zoonotic pathogens can be identified by peripheral blood smear (PBS) examination, using an optical microscope (with a 100× objective) equipped with a digital camera connected to a high-resolution monitor.

The PBS is a basic, inexpensive exam, but its results depend largely on the observer's experience. Among its main advantages, the direct visualization of the pathogen stands out, which confirms a current infection. In addition, it allows the degree of severity of the infection, the microbial load and the involvement

of blood cells. In addition to Bacteria and Parasites, microscopy allows the identification of Fungi. What is not possible to visualize are Viruses, Rickettsias, Coxiella, Francisella tularensis and Neoehrlichia, because they are very small, and Toxoplasma and Chlamydia are difficult to detect with this technique.

MATERIALS AND METHODS.

Blood samples were obtained at the patients' homes. Capillary blood drops were taken from the distal area of the fingers or earlobe. The inclusion criteria were: 1) Have as their main diagnosis: ME/CFS, CFS or MS; 2) Not have been diagnosed exclusively as Long COVID or Long COVID (patients with ME/CFS or MS prior to Long COVID did meet the criteria); 3) Not have as diagnoses: Post-treatment Lyme Disease Syndrome (PTLDS), Fibromyalgia, Multiple Sclerosis (MS) or Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis (ALS), and; 4) To have delivered a properly performed smear sheet.

The search for bacteria, parasites and fungi was carried out by veterinarian Walter Tarello, who has more than 30 years of experience in PBS microscopy.

RESULTS.

A total of 392 PBS received between 2024 and 2026 met the inclusion criteria. In 383 of them (97.7%) at least one pathogenic microorganism was identified in capillary blood by light microscopy. Patients came mainly from Europe (79%), as well as North America (13%: 12% USA and 1% Canada), Australia (4%), Asia (3%: Russia and Turkey) and South Africa (1%). Table 1 shows the pathogenic microorganisms identified and their percentages, calculated on the total of 392 smears.

The two most frequently identified microorganisms were the Babesia parasite in 77.3% of cases (303/392), followed by Bartonella bacteria in 67.3% (264/392).

This was followed by hemotropic Mycoplasmas bacteria (some of which were observed adhering to the erythrocyte membrane) with 32.9% (in 129 out of 392), followed by Borrelia in 30.9% (121/392).

Then Microsporidia in 6.1% (24/392). In 3.6% (14/392) micrococci (corresponding to Staphylococcus). Anaplasma in 3.1% (12/392). Malassezia and Ehrlichia, both at 2.3% (9/392); Candida with 1.5% (6/392). With frequencies less than 1.5%, Plasmodium (vivax and falciparum), septate hyphae compatible with filamentous fungi and Toxoplasma were observed.

In 2.3% (9/392) no pathogens were identified.

Table 1. Frequency of pathogenic microorganisms identified in the 392 patients with ME/CFS by microscopy of capillary blood smears

Pathogenic microorganisms	%
BABESIA (parasite, protozoan type)	77.3
BARTONELLA (bacterium)	67.3
MYCOPLASMA (bacterium, hemotropic)	32.9
BORRELIA (bacterium, spirochetes type)	30.9
MICROSPORIDIA (fungus, that parasitizes)	6.1
STAPHYLOCOCCUS (bacterium, Micrococci)	3.6
ANAPLASMA (bacterium)	3.1
MALASSEZIA (fungus, which parasitizes)	2.3
EHRlichia (bacterium)	2.3
CANDIDA (fungus)	1.5
Others: Plasmodium, Hyphae (fungus), other	2.3
NO PATHOGENS VISUALIZED	2.3

* Viruses, Rickettsia, Coxiella. Francisella tularensis, and Neoehrlichia, are not detected by microscopy.

ZOONOSES ARE COMMON AND TREATABLE OF MYALGIC ENCEPHALOMYELITIS/ CHRONIC FATIGUE SYNDROME (ME/CFS). Aguirre-Chang, Gustavo; Tarello, Walter and Trujillo, Aurora. ResearchGate. January 8, 2026.

The percentages shown in the Table 1 add up to more than 100% because in 77.0% of the PBS (302/392) 2 or more pathogens were identified in the same patient, that is, coinfections.

Table 2 shows the number of pathogenic microorganisms identified per patient with ME/CFS in 392 capillary PBS. The most frequent coinfection was Babesia and Bartonella. Of the cases in which Borrelia was detected, at least one coinfection was identified in 100% (121/121). Coinfections were detected in 86.8% (112/129) of Mycoplasma cases. For Bartonella, it was in 81.8% (216/264), and for Babesia, in 72.9% (221/303) had coinfections.

Table 2. Number of pathogenic microorganisms identified per patient with ME/CFS in 392 capillary Peripheral Blood Smears

Number of pathogenic microorganisms identified	Nro of smears	% of smears
0, no pathogen identified	9	2.3
1 pathogen identified	81	20.7
2 pathogens identified	150	38.3
3 pathogens identified	85	21.7
4 pathogens identified	64	16.3
5 pathogens identified	3	0.8

Table 3 shows the pathogenic microorganisms identified with their corresponding number and percentage, taking as a total the 383 patients with ME/CFS in whom at least one pathogen was detected in the capillary PBS by optical microscopy.

Table 3. Distribution of pathogenic microorganisms in the 383 patients with ME/CFS who had at least one pathogen in capillary blood

Pathogenic microorganisms	Nro	%
BABESIA (parasite, type protozoan)	303	79.5
BARTONELLA (bacterium)	264	69.3
MYCOPLASMA (bacterium)	129	33.9
BORRELIA (bacterium, spirochetes)	121	31.8
MICROSPORIDIA (fungus)	24	6.3
STAPHYLOCOCCUS (bacterium)	14	3.7
ANAPLASMA (bacterium)	12	3.1
MALASSEZIA (fungus)	9	2.4
EHRlichia (bacterium)	9	2.4
Others: Candida, Plasmodium, Hyphae	15	3.9

A direct correlation was observed between symptom severity and a higher number of coinfections. Therefore, bedridden patients diagnosed with severe or very severe ME/CFS frequently had more than two coinfections. A direct correlation was also observed between symptom severity and a higher microbial load (greater quantity) and the higher percentage of blood cells affected by pathogens.

Patients received treatment against the identified pathogens. For Babesia alone, Atavaquone/Proguanil y/o Tafenoquine + Azithromycin or Clarithromycin + Cryptolepis sanguin. were prescribed, sometimes plus Clindamycin. If only Bartonella was present Minocycline + Rifampicin and/or Azithromycin or Clarithromycin + Houttuynia cordata was given. For coinfections with Borrelia, Bartonella, and Babesia, the addition of Dapsone and Pyrazinamide was proposed, sometimes with the addition of Ceftriaxone; Allicin, Resveratrol, Baicalin, cinnamon, Polygonum c.; supplements such as Leucovorin, Vitamin D, Glutathione, Methylene blue, Probiotics for SIBO; and fibrinolytics such as Lumbrokinase. Treated patients experienced improvement in their symptoms, but those most severely affected and with the highest microbial load required several treatment cycles over several months. Microscopic examinations were performed on a group of patients. It was observed that as the severity of the infection decreased, the symptoms of ME/CFS improved.

COMPARASION GROUP (GENERAL ASYMPTOMATIC POPULATION).

In this observational study, the prevalence of current hemopathogenic infection in the general asymptomatic population, mainly represented by healthy blood donors, was used as a comparison group. This population serves as a reference for individuals without a diagnosis of known chronic disease.

Available studies indicate that the prevalence of current detectable infection by these pathogens in blood donors is very low. By performing an analysis of the studies carried out for the detection of Babesia in blood donations and also considering other hemopathogens such as Bartonella and Mycoplasma, it can be conservatively estimated that the prevalence of current infection by any type of hemopathogen in the general asymptomatic population is less than 5%. In contrast, current hemopathogenic infection was identified in 97.7% of patients diagnosed with ME/CFS and/or Long COVID. This marked difference between the prevalence observed in patients and that reported in the general asymptomatic population reinforces the association between these infections and the clinical pictures evaluated.

CONCLUSIONS:

- In 97.7% of patients evaluated with ME/CFS, bacterial, parasites, and/or fungal infections were confirmed by direct visualization by capillary PBS microscopic, which contrasts sharply with prevalence rates in the general asymptomatic population (less than 5%).
- The most frequently identified pathogenic microorganisms were Babesia, Bartonella, Mycoplasma, and Borrelia, so we can affirm that persistent infections by these hemopathogens are the frequent cause of ME/CFS in patients from Europe and North America.
- Co-infections were common, with 77% of patients having 2 or more coexisting infections. The most frequent co-infection was Babesia and Bartonella.
- The PBS performed by an experienced professional, is a test that should be done on all patients with ME/CFS. This is in addition to molecular tests and other tests for the specific detection of hemopathogens.

The authors of this document have not received any grants or financial support from institutions or laboratories.

If this document was helpful to you, please donate to continue our scientific activities:

https://www.paypal.com/donate/?hosted_button_id=4G5KX8377QP6W

APPENDIX 1: OPTICAL MICROSCOPY PHOTOS OF CAPILLARY PERIPHERAL BLOOD SMEARS (PBS) FROM PATIENTS WITH ME/CFS.

**Case 1: Country: Switzerland. Sex: Female. Diag.: CFS
Pathogens identified by optical microscopy:
Bartonella, Mycoplasma and Babesia.**

ZOONOSES ARE COMMON AND TREATABLE OF MYALGIC ENCEPHALOMYELITIS/ CHRONIC FATIGUE SYNDROME (ME/CFS). Aguirre-Chang, Gustavo; Tarello, Walter and Trujillo, Aurora. ResearchGate. January 8, 2026.

Case 3: Country: USA. Sex: Female. Diagnosis: ME/CFS
Pathogens identified by optical microscopy:
Babesia (grade 4) and Mycoplasma (grade 2)

ZOONOSES ARE COMMON AND TREATABLE OF MYALGIC ENCEPHALOMYELITIS/ CHRONIC FATIGUE SYNDROME (ME/CFS). Aguirre-Chang, Gustavo; Tarello, Walter and Trujillo, Aurora. ResearchGate. January 8, 2026.

Case 4: Country: Turkey. Sex: Female. Diagn: ME/CFS
Pathogens identified by microscopy:
Babesia, Borrelia, and Mycoplasma. Serologically positive for Borrelia and Toxoplasmosis.

Case 3: Country: United Kingdom. Sex: Male.
Diagnosis: CFS
Pathogens identified by Microscopy:
Babesia and Bartonella (grade 3).

ZOONOSES ARE COMMON AND TREATABLE OF MYALGIC ENCEPHALOMYELITIS/ CHRONIC FATIGUE SYNDROME (ME/CFS). Aguirre-Chang, Gustavo; Tarello, Walter and Trujillo, Aurora. ResearchGate. January 8, 2026.

Case 4: Country: France. Sex: Female. Diagnosis: CFS, POTS, tinnitus, joint pain, blurred vision. Pathogens identified by microscopy: Bartonella, Borrelia, and Babesia..

ANNEX 2:

HOW TO PERFORM PERIPHERAL BLOOD SMEAR MICROSCOPY WITH DR. WALTER TARELLO.

Optical microscopy is a quick and inexpensive technique, but its results depend heavily on the observer's experience.

Dr. Walter Tarello has been performing this test on humans and animals for over 30 years, which he details in his book titled: Chronic Fatigue

(<https://www.amazon.com/-/es/Chronic-Fatigue-Forgot-Epidemic-revived/dp/1662946813>).

To arrange the shipment of your blood smear, you must write to your personal mail: tarellow@gmail.com he is located in Dubai, United Arab Emirates.

The videos at the following links explain how to properly collect a finger prick sample and spread the blood onto slides to obtain blood smears: <https://youtu.be/7nT7th2WxnE>
<https://youtu.be/bd4eAM5MOik>

Microscope slides for viewing under a microscope are sold at pharmacies. Purchase 4 to 5 slides. The small coverslips are not necessary, only the slides. Fixatives and stains are also unnecessary.

The PBS of patients with the following conditions are also examined under a microscope: Post-Vaccination Syndrome, MIS-C or PIMS, PTLDS, PANS, POTS, Dysautonomia, EDS, MCAS, rheumatoid, juvenile and psoriatic arthritis, MS, ALS, SFN, autoimmune, rheumatological, neurological and psychiatric diseases are also examined under a microscope.